

Investigating the Relationship Between Students' Engagement in Self-Directed Learning and Lifelong Learning in Higher Education

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Abstract: Lifelong learning and self-directed learning are intricately entwined; the necessity for consistent self-improvement and flexibility is recognized by self-directed learning that embraces lifelong learning as a guiding concept. The present study aims to investigate the relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning in the English department of Moulay Ismail university, Morocco. Throughout this research, there has been an exploratory investigation of the relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. To attain this objective, a questionnaire was adopted based on standardized scales. The participants involved in this study were 120 undergraduates from the faculty of Arts and Humanities for the academic year 2023. Convenient sampling was used to select the respondents of the study. A self-rating scale of self-directed learning from Swapna Naskar Williamson (2007) and the other one of lifelong learning from John R. Kirby et al. (2010) were adopted to attain the research objectives. The data was quantitatively analyzed through frequency distribution and percentages, Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Regression Analysis using SPSS software. The results connoted a reciprocal and predictive relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. Considering these findings, some pertinent implications have been provided.

Key words: self-directed learning, lifelong-learning, higher education, global market, soft skills, digital advancement.

Introduction.

Implementing a new lifelong learning paradigm requires learning autonomy; a crucial competence of adult learners according to philosophical, psychological, pedagogical, and Andragogical angles. This paradigm is based on enabling adult learners to participate in the organization of educational events, setting their learning objectives, and implementing their initiatives and agentic self, aiming at self-development, thus helping adult learners to be lifelong learners (Gavrilyuk, 2015).

Knowles (1975) affirms that the traditional education frameworks proved less effective in preparing adult learners for the multifaceted challenges of today's world. Therefore, it is essential to convert from a statically receptive to a proactive approach to learning and teaching. Specifically, adopting the self-directed learning (SDL) approach that leverages natural, cognitive, and personal growth mechanisms.

Adding to this melee, Towle and Cottrell (1996) underlie that the capacity to get hold of self-directed learning skills is a linkage between undergraduate education, postgraduate training, and continuing professional development. Besides, Self-directed learning (SDL) encompasses all learning areas and has a big chance of resulting in transformative learning experiences. Self-directed learning notions are founded on adult learning principles and experiential learning that develop lifetime learning skills (Charokar & Dulloo, 2022). These transformative learning processes, which progress lifelong learning, are partly fostered through critical analysis and self-activeness. Jones and Candy (1993) emphasized that being a self-directed learner manifests mainly

in the conception of learning goals, critical reflection, and the appliance of self-discipline. These attributes primarily corroborate students' lifelong learning skills.

Rationale

Higher education, considering today's pivotal changes, should consider university as a gate to bridging learners into the global market and lifelong learning rather than a certificate accredited after completing a set of modules. In light of that, the relationship between these two variables has not been complementarily explored, a concern that necessitates further investigation.

Self-directed learning approaches and competencies mediate the progression of lifelong learning. Having said that, it is pivotal to determine the relationship between engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong and investigate, including causality, if any. That way, we would reframe higher education traditional viewpoint to an inclusive one. With this attained, this study is anticipated to contribute to the field of adult education, personal development, and tertiary education by unveiling self-directed learning approaches worthiness within the scope of higher education in sustaining lifelong learning tendencies within the global market.

Statement of the problem

Based on the existing literature, previous studies on self-directed learning conducted by notable researchers such as Malcolm Knowles (1975), Candy (1993), Roberson (2005), and Ralph G. Brockett (1991) have primarily focused on descriptive analyses. This reveals a shortage of correlational studies, particularly given the prominent roles that self-directed learning and lifelong learning play in the contemporary landscape of education and society.

In response to this gap in knowledge, this research aims to investigate the connection between undergraduate English department students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. By doing so, it seeks to offer fresh insights into the existing body of research in the field of adult education, with the goal of fostering self-directed learning (SDL) and cultivating lifelong learning (LLL) among adult learners.

Research questions

The present article aims to answer the following questions:

Is there a relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning (SDL) and lifelong learning (LLL)?

Is engagement in self-directed learning a predictor of engagement in lifelong learning?

Research objectives

Aiming to investigate the relationship between undergraduate students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning, the objectives of this study are the following:

To investigate the relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning.

To investigate whether engagement in self-directed learning is a predictor of engagement in lifelong learning.

Overview of methodology

Drawing on previous studies and articles that are partly related to this research concern, this thesis adopted a purely quantitative approach to achieve its purpose. Therefore, a survey, notably a structured questionnaire, was distributed to English department students to address the research questions. This questionnaire was basically built upon previously standardized scales. In terms of the sampling method, Convenience sampling method was used. Regarding data analysis, correlational analysis and inferential statistics were used. Correlation analysis, namely Pearson Correlation Product-Moment Coefficient r was used to identify any significant relationship between undergraduate English department students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. As for inferential statistics, linear regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of engagement in self-directed learning on lifelong learning.

Chapter one: review of literature

1-1 Definition of key concepts

Self-directed learning has been rehabilitated by various experts and scholars in the higher education context. Throughout our analysis of the literature review, pioneers tackled self-directed learning from different worldviews and educational orientations. And yet, some common premises are universally agreed upon in previous studies.

1-1-1 self-directed learning

Despite how self-directed learning was coined, it is more than just a nomenclature concept. It is a life norm (Brockett & Hiemstra, 1991). The term self-directed learning is directly related to freedom, autonomy, independence, student-centeredness, and critical reflection. It is a new paradigm shift in learning and teaching philosophy (Brookfield, 1985). It is consistent progress in which learners take the inauguration, either with the assistance of others or not, to identify their learning needs, implement learning aims, identify human and material resources for learning, put into use learning strategies, and evaluate learning objectives (Knowles, 1975).

According to Brockett and Hiemstra (1991), self-direction is feasible in any learning-teaching environment. Making adult learners control their learning is a way to encourage learning. Conceptually, Roberson (2005) held that self-directed learning might come alternatively as self-planned learning, inquiry method, independent learning, self-education, self-instruction, self-teaching, self-study, and autonomous learning. Still, self-directed learning differs from the previous terms in that it might mutually include the help of preceptors, mentors, and peers in a constructivist way. In this regard, self-directed learning includes initiation of learning process, identification of learning needs, developing learning goals, selecting and implementing learning strategies, determining how to measure learning goals (Knowles, 1975, as cited in Boyer et al., 2014). Still, self-directed learning is not solely a matter of applying learning techniques and strategies but also of changing learners' perspectives, superseding learners' paradigms, and adapting to the real world (Leach, n.d.). According to Knowles (1975), self-directed learning assumes five key assumptions:

- A- The necessity of human growth in capacity and needs as a pivotal component in maturing.
- B- Learners' experiences constitute a rich resource for learning.
- C- Readiness in learning what is required to learn and resolve problems.
- D- Self-directedness evolves problem-centeredness.

E- Internal incentives, such as self-esteem, are radical in the continuity of self-directed learning.

To conclude, self-directed learning has been defined differently by several scholars and researchers. And yet, a concurrence was yielded throughout the studies, especially that sets of characteristics and learning competencies are agreeably established about higher education. The pre-given conceptions were a means to develop an understanding of what self-directed learning includes. That would help to establish a set of competencies that go in parallel with the construct.

1-1-2 lifelong learning

In short, lifelong learning is one of the most pervasive concepts in adult education, which denotes the learning process throughout a lifespan. Lifelong learning is quintessential to keeping up with the changes in the world and is often portrayed as the field of inquiry in the scope of adult education. Considering the current changes in education and technology, lifelong learning has become a necessity for development and growth. And the question that arises is whether people are ready for change, adaptation, and learning (Jarvis, 2012).

Lifelong learning refers to the idea that learning goes beyond formal education to entail a person's life. It has been seen as a natural pursuit for humans throughout life to gain new knowledge. Lifelong learning encompasses different contexts, not only instructional settings. To date, the concept of lifelong learning and lifelong education have gained importance in recent years owing to the technological revolution and change. Consequently, lifelong learning is essential to adapt to these changes (Candy et al., 1994). Analogously, lifelong learning is a consistent process influenced by an individual's experience. Therefore, it is crucial to prioritize individuals' experiences, taking into consideration the combination of personal traits, experiences, and the uninterrupted impact of experiences as so-called micro-genesis or moment by-moment learning throughout an individual's life (Billett, 2018).

The lifelong learning process presents a unique opportunity for discovery rather than remaining stationary in habitual patterns. It is constant exploration, inquiry, and personal growth. The lifelong learner can pursue personal development variously without necessarily being in a four-wall classroom (Gross, 1977). Along the same lines, the effectiveness of lifelong learning, which includes formal, non-formal, and informal learning, lies basically to the extent to which higher education helps learners to extend academic freedom, exploratory learning, and knowledge facilities (Gavrilyuk, 2015).

1-2 measurement scales

Numerous distinguished academics and scholars attempted to develop self-rating measurement scales within the corpus of existing research and theoretical foundations to appraise students' skills for self-directed learning and lifelong learning. A systematic inspection of the measurement scales conducted in scientific investigations has been unveiled in the ensuing paragraphs to get a thorough understanding of the competencies that underline them. These scales are choral methodological instruments that confer the researchers attain research objectives. A variety of scales with carefully prepared items developed by esteemed and eminent professors are designed to gauge students' levels of self-directed learning and lifelong learning. These scales are elaborately plaited around a range of competencies.

1-2-1 self-directed learning:

In what should come first, Xuan et al. (2018) investigated self-directed learning readiness among university students learning English. The study was constituted of three primary constructs, namely motivation, awareness, and learning strategies. In terms of methodology and instruments, a survey questionnaire was administered, particularly, a 6-point Likert-Like measurement scale and many items were adapted and refined according to some existing instruments, namely the Learner Autonomy Readiness Instrument (LARI) (Kocak, 2003), Self-Rating Scales of Self-Directed Learning (SRSSDL) (Williamson, 2007), Self-directed Learning Readiness Scale (SDLRS) (Steward and Yan, 2007). According to Hoban et al. (2005), to detect the relationship between variables, a principal axis factor analysis with oblique rotation was used on the 58 SDLRS items, and a set of confirmatory factor analyses using LISREL 8.54 was performed to examine the dimension of SDLRS. The instrument used in this area was the Self-Directed Learning Readiness Scale (SDLRS), a 40-item Likert-type questionnaire implemented to gauge learners' readiness for self-directed learning.

In a parallel manner, in a similar study, two prime constructs have been used to assess and measure self-directed learning skills among pre-service teachers: awareness and self-efficacy (Acar et al., 2016).

1-2-2 life-long learning:

Measurement of lifelong learning tendencies has been done through statistical measures.

Content validity was tested through expert opinion. Concurrent validity was tested by measuring the correlation between the lifelong tendency scale and the Curiosity Index. Construct validity was determined through exploratory factor analysis. Cronbach's alpha value was used to indicate internal consistency. Most importantly, the lifelong learning scale includes four factors that can be considered in this research: motivation, perseverance, regulated learning, and curiosity (Coşkun & Demirel, 2010). In a study that sought to develop a reliable and valid questionnaire based on five constructs or characteristics of lifelong learners identified by Knapper and Cropley, 14 items have been used to measure lifelong learning among university and vocational college students. In constructing the items, the five dimensions devised by Candy have been considered as the following: goal setting, application of knowledge and skills, self-direction and self-evaluation, information location, and learning strategy adaptation (Kirby et al., 2010). These items used proved reliable; Cronbach alpha reliability was 0.77.

1-3 The relationship between self-directed learning and lifelong learning

Although few studies have addressed this relationship, researchers indicate its reciprocity. The competencies that underlie them tend to overlap, making it possible that the relationship is expected to be congruent.

An advanced understanding of teaching and learning enables students to be self-directed learners, thus developing lifelong learning skills. Self-directed learning readiness appears to be a mediator of lifelong learning (Karataş et al., 2021). According to Tekkol and Demirel (2018), self-directed learning is considered a dimension of lifelong learning. Self-directed learning skills include setting goals, planning, taking the initiative, openness to learning, self-motivation, and confidence. All of which sustain life-lifelong learning tendencies. From a pedagogical point of view, self-directed learning philosophy lies inherently in providing faculty training and mentorship programs (Charokar & Dulloo, 2022).

Drawing on previous literature, the relationship between the two variables is neither well-grounded in solid foundations nor thoroughly determined. According to Van Rensburg and Botma (2015), further research is needed to determine the relationship between self-directed learning and lifelong learning.

Chapter two: Methodology

This chapter was devoted to setting ground for the practical aspect of this research paper. It is attained by outlining the research design, detailing the procedures for data collection and presenting the strategies involved for data analysis. The reliability and validity of the scales used were pinpointed to ensure the credibility of this study evolved around these two research questions:

Is there a relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning (SDL) and lifelong learning (LLL)?

Is engagement in self-directed learning a predictor of engagement in lifelong learning?

2-1 Research design

The research design employed in this study is quantitative, aiming to investigate the interconnection between undergraduate English department students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. In this regard, this research paper is both correlational and predictive as it is centered on collecting and analyzing numerical data to determine whether the relationship between engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning traces a positive or negative direction. This research is cross-sectional, intending to generalize the sample to the whole population, and exploratory, seeking to develop general insights and conclusions.

2-2 Settings and participants

The study consisted of a sample size (n) of 120 undergraduate English department students distributed across semester 2, semester 4, and semester 6. The sample comprised 58,3% of females and 41,7% of males. In terms of the Sampling method used, Convenience sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique where respondents were selected based on their accessibility and availability, was adopted to collect data without the need for extensive sampling procedures and to ensure access to the participants based on their availability and accessibility.

2-4 Research instruments

In this study, the researcher adopted a questionnaire based on standardized scales to collect data and to investigate the relationship between engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. The questionnaire was written in English and contains 21 items. It was adopted from two sources: a self-rating scale of self-directed learning devised by Swapna Naskar Williamson (2007) and a measurement scale of lifelong learning by John R. Kirby et al. (2010). The questionnaire items were based on criteria consistent with the literature review and agreed upon by renowned scholars. In the questionnaire, a five-point Likert scale questions were adopted in which the responses ranged from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree'. The questionnaire consisted of three main parts: part 1 for identifying demographic variables, part 2 for measuring students' engagement in self-directed learning, and part 3 for measuring students' engagement in lifelong learning. It is worth noting that the questionnaire was administered to students online.

The two self-directed learning and lifelong learning scales adopted in this study were adapted from Swapna Naskar Williamson (2007) and John R. Kirby et al. (2010). The internal consistency of the two scales was highly reliable. The researcher further simplified some items of the two scales accordingly to make it manageable for the participants to fill out. Evaluating the internal consistency of the scales using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, the results indicated a high rate of

internal consistency with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0,83, indicating that the questionnaire is highly reliable. Regarding validity, the researcher assumes that the two scales, which comprised the questionnaire, have content validity since it was adopted from Swapna Naskar Williamson (2007) and John R. Kirby et al. (2010), who based their scales upon the consensus and the accreditation of esteemed scholars.

Table 4

Reliability Test of Internal Consistency

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.838	18

Regarding inferential statistics, given the interval scale, Pearson’s correlation coefficient and regression analysis were used. According to Jr and Boone (2012), parametric tests should be used in this case “Additional data analysis procedures appropriate for interval scale items would include the Pearson's r and regression procedures” (p.4). Similarly, according to Joshi et al. (2015), Likert-scale data can be analyzed through parametric tests, especially when calculating the items to generate a composite score of a set of items that fall under a research variable; therefore, the assigned scale will be interval and measures central tendency and standard deviation. Parametric tests were used. Sullivan and Artino (2013) further confirm that parametric tests are more robust than nonparametric. They provide the right answer even when statistical assumptions, such as normal distribution of data- are violated.

Chapter three: Data analysis and discussion

The data was collected through a questionnaire, which consists of 21 Likert scale items. The questionnaire items were divided into two main sections. The first section, which included 12 items, measured students’ engagement in self-directed learning. The second section, which included 6 items, measures students’ engagement in lifelong learning, plus the three items of age, gender, and educational level.

3-1 The relationship between students’ engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning

The nature of these research variables at hand, after computing the composite scores, are quantitatively interval. SPSS has transformed the variables into new ones after computing the scores of the items related to self-directed learning and lifelong learning so that a correlational analysis would be feasible. In addition, these research variables are quantitative, linear, and measured on a scale measurement. Given these conditions, Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation was conducted to assess the strength of the relationship, if any. This study was partly oriented based on a study conducted by Tekkol and Demirel (2018), where the self-directed learning scale and lifelong learning scale were used to collect students’ scores, and in determining the relationship between the two research variables, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used as was the case with our study.

The SPSS output of Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient is as follows:

Table 1

The Results of Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between SDL and LLL

	Self-directed learning	lifelong learning
Pearson Correlation	1	.605**
self-directed learning Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	120	120
Pearson Correlation	.605**	1
lifelong learning Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 reveals the correlation between self-directed learning and lifelong learning.

Descriptively, the mean score of self-directed learning is $r = 4.01, p < .05$, and of lifelong learning is $r = 3.97, p < .05$. The first value “.605” tells us the strength of this relationship, The value “1” represented in the columns of self-directed learning and lifelong learning indicates that there is a positive relationship between self-directed learning and lifelong learning. It also means that these two research variables are linear and are exactly on a straight line. The value of “.605” indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between self-directed learning and lifelong learning. The correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), given that the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, which means that the relationship is positively significant. In other words, the p-value confirms the correlation between the research variables. It indicates that the correlation between self-directed learning and lifelong learning is statistically significant, indicating that the observed relationship is unlikely to occur by chance. Individuals who exhibit higher levels of self-directed learning tend to engage more in lifelong learning. In other words, there is a strong positive relationship between students’ engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. To this end, these two variables are complementary to one another.

Our study suggests that students who are engaged in self-directed learning are more likely to be motivated to pursue their learning and be better equipped to identify and continue learning opportunities throughout their lives. In a way, self-directed learning is a key component of lifelong learning, as it grants individuals the competencies to track their learning. Individuals can identify, rectify, and fulfill their learning needs and acquire new skills and knowledge at an ongoing rate instead of hinging upon formal education.

3-2 The predictability of students’ engagement in self-directed learning on their engagement in lifelong learning

The study sought to investigate whether students’ engagement in self-directed learning is a predictor of their engagement in lifelong learning. The objective of these research questions was to investigate whether engagement in self-directed learning is a predictive variable of students’ engagement in lifelong learning.

Simple linear regression was conducted in this study as we have one independent variable, engagement in self-directed learning, and wanted to see whether it predicts the dependent variable, engagement in lifelong learning. Simpler linear regression, which is an extension of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, was conducted. This analysis of the question is significantly related to the previous question analysis, which indicated a positively significant relationship. Simple Linear Regression was conducted to investigate this research question and to gain deeper insights into that. The SPSS output of Simple Linear Regression is as follows:

Overall, as far as engagement in self-directed learning is correlated with engagement in lifelong learning, the influence of self-directed learning on lifelong learning is most likely to occur. One cannot assume learners’ engagement in lifelong learning without being, in the first place, engaged in self-directed learning skills, which entail a set of competencies that foster lifelong learning. Self-directed learning is a critical component in the higher education system that needs to be developed among students. This way, we encourage continuous education and foster lifelong learning practices among learners beyond formal education. Having said that, adult learners who exhibit self-directed learning tendencies are more likely to engage in lifelong learning. Self-directed learning is deemed of considerable prominence given the skills that intersect with lifelong learning. Simply put, adult learners who engage in high levels of self-directed learning are more likely to have higher levels of lifelong learning than those who engage in lower levels of self-directed learning. The self-directed learning approach fosters the attitude of lifelong learning, marked by curiosity, adaptability, and progress. The capacity for self-directed learning enables adult learners to adapt to the shifts in education and society to pursue personal and professional development advancement.

Conclusion.

This article has proposed a solid ground for investigating the relationship between students' engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning. Based on quantitative analysis of data, it is concluded that the relationship between engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning is significantly positive. The specific objectives of this study are twofold: investigating the relationship between engagement in self-directed learning and lifelong learning and determining the influence of engagement in self-directed learning on lifelong learning.

Implications.

Student-centered approaches can be cultivated to enhance lifelong learning. As for curriculum design, institutions can integrate opportunities for self-directed learning, such as internships, experiential learning projects, and open-ended assignments. Aligning the curriculum with lifelong learning ideologies will foster intellectual growth among adult learners. The connection between self-directed learning and lifelong learning impacts the development of support services in higher education. Specifically, adopting self-directed learning approaches, institutions can consider providing adult learners with learning resources, mentoring practicums, and exchange programs to promote lifelong learning. This mindset can urge adult learners to utilize available support services and learning facilities to extend their learning beyond the formal context. This approach to learning provides a suitable learning environment that empowers lifelong learning tendencies and enhances educational, personal, and professional landscapes.

The importance of self-directed learning lies considerably in promoting lifelong learning. The advancement of self-directed learning in universities not only promotes adult learners' lifelong learning in occupational contexts but goes beyond that to include liberal and vocational education scopes. Furthermore, the importance of self-directed learning manifests in enhancing critical reflection and proactive, discursive, and mutual engagement among adult learners. The role of the university nowadays should go beyond educational and professional aims to encompass the development of liberal education at the personal level.

The self-directed learning approach is quintessential for promoting democracy, augmenting critical thinking and assessment, and developing lifelong learning tendencies. Self-directed learning chorally enhances critical scrutiny among adult learners to autonomously inquire and appraise *Savoir-faire* and *Savoir-être* to radicalize a judicious attitude. Eventually, educational programs and higher education institutions should provide ample opportunities for adult learners to advance the key competencies that pertain to the self-directed lifelong learning approach. They are recommended to change the traditional teaching methods with teaching philosophies that promote self-direction, including self-inquiry, reflection, interpersonal skills, intrapersonal skills, and learning strategies, thus ensuring personal professional advancements, lifelong learning, anti-social inequality orientations, and critical immune intellect.

Limitations.

No study is without limitations; the present study is no exception. One of the significant limitations of this research is the sample size of this study. It is no more than 120 undergraduate English department students as the accessibility was difficult. The sample size of this research might not be generalizable enough to get the most robust conclusions. Henceforth, further research is needed to investigate this issue using a larger sample size by extending the population to other levels and other disciplines.

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